

Mapping between Q^d and Q^{d+2}

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Abstract

Beckman, F.S and Quarles D.A, have proven in [1], the following theorem: Each function from the d -Euclidean space, ($d \geq 2$) into itself and which maintains distance 1 is an isometry.

In addition, in [7, 8], I had proven the parallel theorem for rational spaces to the previous theorem, namely: every mapping from d -rational into itself, and which maintains distance 1 is an isometry provided $d \geq 5$.

Furthermore, in [6], I had proven: If $d \geq 5$, and if, $\omega(d) = \omega(d+1)$, then every unit-distance preserving mapping Q^d into Q^{d+1} is an isometry, add to that, gave a form for the dimension d for which $\omega(d) = \omega(d+1)$.

Here in this article, I will expand one last result to show that in some special dimension d , every unit distance-preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ is an isometry.

In addition, which are the dimension d for which $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$?

Introduction

Let (X, d) and (Y, ρ) be two metric spaces, and let f be a map $f: (X, d) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$, if for all x, y in (X, d) , and for a real number $b > 0$, from $d(x, y) = b$, implies that

$d(f(x), f(y)) = b$, then f is called b -distance preserving. Moreover, if the map saves all the distance $b > 0$ then f is an isometry.

Let $\omega(d)$ denote the clique number of the graph that has Q^d as its set of vertices, and where two vertices x and y are connected by edge if and only if $\|x - y\| = 1$.

New result:

The intent of this article is to prove that in certain dimensions d , every unit distance-preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ is an isometry.

Our main results are the following Theorems:

Theorem 1:

If $d \geq 5$, and if, $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$, then every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ is an isometry.

After we prove this sentence, we will also represent which are the dimension d for which

$\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$?

Based on Lemma 2 (Chilakamarri [2]) that implies if $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$, then

$\omega(d) = \omega(d+2) = n + 1$. Moreover, d must be an odd integer, we prove also the following theorem.

Lemma A:

If $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2) = d + 1$ for an odd integer d , then d is of the form $d = 2k^2 - 1$, provided there exist, no solutions to the Diophantine equation $(d+2)x^2 - 2(d+1)y^2 = z^2$ for which

$x \neq 0$.

Known Lemmas:

The following known Lemmas will be used by us to prove our purpose.

Lemma 1: (J.Zaks [9]).

If $v_1, \dots, v_n, w_1, \dots, w_m$ are points in Q^d , $n \leq m$ such that:

$\|v_i - v_j\| = \|w_r - w_s\|$, for all, $1 \leq i \leq j \leq n$, $1 \leq r \leq s \leq m$, then there exists a congruence $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$, such that $f(v_i) = w_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Lemma 2: (Chilakamarri [2]).

A. For even d , $\omega(d) = d+1$, if $d+1$ is a complete square; otherwise $\omega(d) = d$.

B. For odd d , $d \geq 5$, the value of $\omega(d)$ is as follows: if $d = 2n^2 - 1$, then $\omega(d) = d+1$; if

$d \neq 2n^2 - 1$ and the Diophantine equation $dx^2 - 2(d-1)y^2 = z^2$ has a solution in which $x \neq 0$ then $\omega(d) = d$; otherwise $\omega(d) = d - 1$.

Lemma 3:(W.hibi [3]).

If a, b, c are three numbers that satisfy the triangle inequality and if a^2, b^2, c^2 are rational numbers then:

a. , and

b. The space $Q^d, d \geq 8$ contains a triangle ABC , having edge length: $AB=c, BC=a, AC=b$.

Corollary 1: (W.hibi [3]). $(a^2 + b^2 + c^2)^2$

If a, b, l satisfy the triangle inequality and if a^2, b^2 are rational numbers, then the space Q^d contains the vertices of a triangle which has edge lengths a, b, l .

Corollary 2:(W.hibi [3]).

If t is a number such that $\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1 \leq t \leq \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1, t^2 \in Q$

Where $m \geq 4$ is a natural number, then the space $Q^d, d \geq 5$, contains a triangle ABC having edge length $l, t, \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}}$.

Lemma 4: (W.hibi [3]).

If x and y are two points in $Q^d, d \geq 5$, so that:

$$\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1 \leq |x - y| \leq \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$$

Where $\omega(d) = m$, then there exists a finite set $S(x,y)$, contains x and y such that $f(x) \neq f(y)$ holds for every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: S(x,y) \rightarrow Q^d$.

Lemma 5: (due to W.hibi [6]).

If x and y are two points in $Q^d, d \geq 5$, so that:

$$\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1 \leq |x - y| \leq \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$$

Where $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 1) = m$, then there exists a finite set $F(x,y)$, contains x and y such that $f(x) \neq f(y)$ holds for every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: F(x,y) \rightarrow Q^d$.

Conclusion from Lemma 5:

If x and y are two points in $Q^d, d \geq 5$, so that:

$$\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1 < |x - y| < \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$$

Where $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = m$, then there exists a finite set $J(x,y)$ in Q^d , contains x and y such that $f(x) \neq f(y)$ holds for every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: J(x,y) \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$.

New results:

Theorem 1:

If $d \geq 5$, and if, $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$, then every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ is an isometry.

Proof of Theorem 1:

Let $d \geq 5$, and let $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = m$.

We will divide the proof into several steps:

Step 1:

We will show that if Z, W are any two points in Q^d , for which $|Z - W| = \sqrt{2}$, then there exists a finite set M_d in Q^d contains Z and W such that for every unit-distance preserving mapping

$f: M_d \rightarrow Q^{d+1}, |f(Z) - f(W)| = |Z - W|$ holds, this shows that every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves the distance $\sqrt{2}$.

We obtain the following assertions:

Case (a):

If d is odd:

Consider the $(d - 1)$ points $\{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}\}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}, 0 \right) \\ A_2 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0 \right) \\ A_3 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0 \right) \\ A_4 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0 \right) \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

$$A_{d-2} = \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0, 0\right)$$

$$A_{d-1} = \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0, 0\right)$$

The points $\{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}\}$ form the vertices of a regular $(d-2)$ -simplex of edge length one in Q^d . Let the $(d-1)$ points B_1, B_2, \dots, B_{d-1} of Q^d , be defined by $B_i = -A_i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$, their mutual distances are one, so they form the vertices of a regular $(d-2)$ -simplex of edge length one in Q^d .

Let T_d denote the set $T_d = \{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}, B_1, \dots, B_{d-1}\}$. Fix a $k, 1 \leq k \leq d-1$, by Lemma 1 and based on $\|Z - W\| = \|A_k - B_k\|$ there exist a rational congruence h for which:

$h(A_k) = Z := A_k^*$, and $h(B_k) = W := B_k^*$. Denote $h(A_i) = A_i^*$ and $h(B_i) = B_i^*$ for all $1 \leq i \leq d-1$, and let $T_d^* = \{A_1^*, \dots, A_{d-1}^*, B_1^*, \dots, B_{d-1}^*\}$, it is clear that $Z, W \in T_d^*$.

Denote the set $M_d = S(A_1^*, B_1^*) \cup S(A_2^*, B_2^*) \cup \dots \cup S(A_{d-1}^*, B_{d-1}^*)$.

Let $f: M_d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ be any unit-distance preserving mapping.

Claim 1:

If x and y are two points in T_d^* , then $f(x) \neq f(y)$.

Proof of Claim 1:

Computing the mutual distance of the points in T_d^* shows that:

$\|A_i^* - A_j^*\| = \|B_i^* - B_j^*\| = \|A_i^* - B_j^*\| = 1$, for all $1 \leq i < j \leq d-1$, and $\|A_i^* - B_i^*\| = \sqrt{2}$, for all $1 \leq i \leq d-1$.

All of the distances above are between $\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1$ and $\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$. Therefore, if $\|x - y\| = 1$, then $\|f(x) - f(y)\| = 1$, hence $f(x) \neq f(y)$, if $\|x - y\| = \sqrt{2}$ there is an $i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$, such that $x = A_i^*, y = B_i^*$ and $\|A_i^* - B_i^*\| = \sqrt{2}$.

By Conclusion from Lemma 5, applied to A_i^* and B_i^* , there exist a set $S(A_i^*, B_i^*)$, that contains A_i^* and B_i^* , for which every unit-distance preserving mapping $g: S(A_i^*, B_i^*) \rightarrow Q^d$ satisfies $g(A_i^*) \neq g(B_i^*)$.

In particular, this holds for the mapping $g = f$ restricted to $S(A_i^*, B_i^*)$, therefore $f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*)$.

Claim 2:

$\|f(A_i^*) - f(B_i^*)\| < 2$, holds for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$.

Proof of Claim 2:

According to Claim 1, $f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*)$ for every i .

First, we will show that: $\|f(A_i^*) - f(B_i^*)\| \leq 2$ for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$.

Let S be the unit sphere, centered at the point $f(A_j^*)$, when $j \neq i$ and $j \leq d-1$, it is clear that this unit sphere contains the two points $f(A_i^*)$ and $f(B_i^*)$, because

$\|f(A_j^*) - f(B_i^*)\| = \|f(A_j^*)\| = 1$ When $j \neq i, j \leq d-1$.

That is, $f(A_i^*), f(B_i^*) \in S$, therefore $\|f(A_i^*) - f(B_i^*)\| \leq 2$.

Suppose that there exists an $i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$ so that $\|f(A_i^*) - f(B_i^*)\| = 2$. The midpoint of the segment $[f(A_i^*), f(B_i^*)]$ is the unique rational point which is at distance one from both of the two points $f(A_i^*)$ and $f(B_i^*)$.

The points $f(A_j^*)$ and $f(B_j^*), j \neq i \leq d-1$, are two points so that the distance of each one of them from $f(A_i^*)$, as well as from $f(B_i^*)$, is also one. Therefore, it follows that

$\frac{1}{2}[f(A_i^*) + f(B_i^*)] = f(A_j^*) = f(B_j^*)$, which is a contradiction to the fact that $f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*)$ for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq d-1$.

Claim 3:

$\|f(Z) - f(W)\| = \sqrt{2}$.

Proof of Claim 3:

Consider the following $(d+1)$ points:

$f(A_3^*), \dots, f(A_{d-2}^*), f(A_{d-1}^*), f(B_{d-4}^*), f(B_{d-3}^*), f(B_{d-2}^*), f(B_{d-1}^*)$.

Each one of the mutual distances between these $(d+1)$ points is less than two because,

$\|f(A_{d-1}^*) - f(B_{d-1}^*)\| < 2, \|f(A_{d-2}^*) - f(B_{d-2}^*)\| < 2, \|f(A_{d-3}^*) - f(B_{d-3}^*)\| < 2,$ and $\|f(A_{d-4}^*) - f(B_{d-4}^*)\| < 2$, according to Claim 2.

The rest of the distances are 1, since f preserves distance 1.

The four points $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$, and $f(B_2^*)$ are in the intersection of the $d+1$ spheres of radius one, centered at the points:

$f(A_3^*), \dots, f(A_{d-2}^*), f(A_{d-1}^*), f(B_{d-4}^*), f(B_{d-3}^*), f(B_{d-2}^*), f(B_{d-1}^*)$.

All the mutual distances of the centers of these spheres are less than 2, hence the $d + 1$ spheres intersect in a one-dimensional sphere, which is a circle. Thus $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$ and $f(B_2^*)$ form the vertex set of a quadrangle, of edge lengths one, that lies in a circle. It follows that $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$, and $f(B_2^*)$ form a square in a circle of diameter $\sqrt{2}$, implying:

$$||f(A_1^*) - f(B_1^*)|| = ||f(A_2^*) - f(B_2^*)|| = \sqrt{2}, \text{ since } f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*) \text{ for } i = 1, 2.$$

It follows by Lemma 1 that the mapping f preserves all the distance $\sqrt{2}$, between A_i^* and B_i^* for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1$. In particular $||f(z) - f(w)|| = \sqrt{2}$.

Case (b):

If d is even:

Consider the d points $\{A_1, \dots, A_d\}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}\right) \\ A_2 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}\right) \\ A_3 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ A_4 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ &\vdots \\ A_{d-1} &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0\right) \\ A_d &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0\right) \end{aligned}$$

The point $\{A_1, \dots, A_d\}$ form the vertices of a regular $(d - 1)$ - simplex of edge length one in Q^d . Let the d points B_1, B_2, \dots, B_d of Q^d be defined by $B_i = -A_i, 1 \leq i \leq d$, their mutual distances are one, so they form the vertices of a regular $(d - 1)$ - simplex of edge length one in Q^d . Let T_d denote the set $T_d = \{A_1, \dots, A_d, B_1, \dots, B_d\}$.

Fix a $k, 1 \leq k \leq d$, by Lemma 1 and based on $||Z - W|| = ||A_k - B_k||$ there exist a rational congruence h for which $h(A_k) = Z := A_k^*$ and $h(B_k) = W := B_k^*$, and denote

$h(A_i) = A_i^*$ and $h(B_i) = B_i^*$ for all $1 \leq i \leq d$. Let $T_d^* = \{A_1^*, \dots, A_d^*, B_1^*, \dots, B_d^*\}$, it is clear that $Z, W \in T_d^*$.

Denote the set $M_d = S(A_1^*, B_1^*) \cup S(A_2^*, B_2^*) \cup \dots \cup S(A_d^*, B_d^*)$.

Let $f: M_d \rightarrow Q^d$ be any unit-distance preserving mapping. The rest follows as in the proof of case (a). (This shows that every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves the distance $\sqrt{2}$).

Step 2:

Now, we will show that every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, also preserves the distance 2.

The mapping f preserves every unit square, since f preserves the distance 1 and $\sqrt{2}$.

Let M_1 and M_2 two squares as above such that $M_1 \perp M_2$, (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

The mapping f preserves the squares M_1 and M_2 .

Since $||A - E|| = ||B - F|| = \sqrt{2}$ then, $||f(A) - f(E)|| = ||f(B) - f(F)|| = \sqrt{2}$,

so the mapping f preserves the configuration as in Figure 1, thus, f preserves right angles, therefore every unit d -dimensional cube on Q^d is mapped to a unit d -dimensional cube on Q^{d+2} . Consider the unit cube that has the 2^d vertices, using only zeros and ones as coordinates, since f preserves it, then f preserves the distance 2 that is a possible distance between this 2^d vertices.

Step 3:

We will show that every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ integer.

Using n collinear points congruent to $\{i: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, (see Figure 2), it follows that the mapping f preserves each one of their distances points, also preserves their collinearity.

Figure 2

Step 4:

We will show that every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves $\sqrt{n}, n \in Z$.
The mapping f is an isometry when restricted to sets congruent to

$$B = \left\{ (i_1, i_2, \dots, i_k) \left| \begin{array}{l} 0 \leq i_j \leq c_j \\ 1 \leq j \leq k \\ 1 \leq k \leq d \\ c_j \geq 5 \end{array} \right. \right\}$$

Since every set of 2^k vertices of a unit k - dimensional cube of B is mapped by f to k -dimensional parallelepiped, but f preserves right angles, therefore this parallelepiped are k -dimensional boxes. For every positive integer n , there is a box B , as defined above, in which the distance of the two farthest points is \sqrt{n} , this follows from $d \geq 5$ and Lagrange's Four Squares Theorem. Thus, the mapping f preserves the distance \sqrt{n} .

Step 5:

Every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves any rational distance.
Suppose that an integer $m \geq 1$ is given, and that the mapping f preserves the distance α .
The mapping f is an isometry on the set, described in Figure 3.

Figure 3

It follows that f preserves the distance α/m .

Step 6:

Finally, we will show that for every two points x and y of Q^d , every unit-distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$, preserves the distance $\|x - y\|$.

Let x and y be any two points in Q^d , it's clear that $\|x - y\| = \sqrt{\frac{p}{q}}$, when p and q , some integers. The mapping f preserves the distance $\sqrt{\frac{p}{q}}$, because $\sqrt{\frac{p}{q}} = \frac{1}{q} \sqrt{pq}$ and the mapping f preserves the distances of the form $\frac{1}{q} \sqrt{pq}$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

The question now, which are the dimensions d for which $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2)$? It follows from Lemma 2 that if $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2)$, then $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = d + 1$ and d must be an odd integer.

Lemma A:

If $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = d + 1$ for an odd integer d , then d is of the form $d = 2k^2 - 1$, provided the exist no solutions to the Diophantine equation $(d + 2)x^2 - 2(d + 1)y^2 = z^2$ for which $x \neq 0$.

Proof of Lemma A:

Let d be an odd integer for which $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = d + 1$.

It follows from $\omega(d) = d + 1$ that d is of the form $d = 2t^2 - 1$.

It follows from $\omega(d + 2) = d + 1$ that $d + 2 \neq 2r^2 - 1$ (i.e., $d \neq 2r^2 - 3$, which follows from the requirement that $d = 2t^2 - 1$), and that there should not exist solutions to the Diophantine equation $(d + 2)x^2 - 2(d - 1)y^2 = z^2$ for which $x \neq 0$.

This completes the proof of Lemma A.

An example of a dimension d for which $\omega(d) = \omega(d + 2) = d + 1$ is $d = 17$, since $\omega(17) = \omega(19) = 18$, as can be easily shown.

Conclusions:

After the result, we got from Theorem 1: If $d \geq 5$, and if, $\omega(d) = \omega(d+2)$, then every unit- distance-preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+2}$ is an isometry, and since we know that: If $d \geq 5$, and if, $\omega(d) = \omega(d+1)$, then every unit- distance-preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+1}$ is an isometry [6].

We wonder is there a proof for, are there conditions on a dimension $d \geq 5$, Checks through it, that every - preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^{d+j}$ is an isometry, $j \geq 3$?"

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